

Development of kinetics of wastewater treatment in the aerobic biofilm reactor

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Biofilm process is widely used for a variety of wastewater especially containing slowly biodegradable substances. It is resistant to toxic environment and capable of excellent retention of biomass under continuous operation. Development of kinetics is very much pertinent for rational design of a biofilm process for the treatment of wastewater with or without inhibitory substances. A simple approach for development of such kinetics for an aerobic biofilm reactor has been presented using a novel biofilm model. The novel biofilm model is formulated from the correlations between substrate concentrations in the influent/effluent and at biofilm liquid interface along with substrate flux and biofilm thickness complying Monod's growth kinetics. The methodology for determining the kinetic coefficients for substrate removal and biomass growth has been demonstrated stepwise along with graphical representation. Kinetic coefficients like K , k , Y , b_t , b_s and b_d are determined either from the intercepts of X and Y-axis or from the slope of the graphical plots.

Keywords: Biofilm process, wastewater treatment, simple model, Monod's kinetics, kinetic coefficient.

Introduction

Biofilms are natural, heterogeneous, multiphase material consisting primarily of microbial cells, insoluble extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) and interstitial water¹ attached on a solid surface which are used to combat high organic strengths in wastewater. Due to some inherent advantages like low energy consumption, easy maintenance, better physical and chemical stability and excellent biomass retention importance of biofilm is increasing in biological treatment of wastewater. A unique feature of biofilm process lies in the operation of continuous flow mode with minimal biomass loss compared to the traditional suspended growth bioreactor. Biofilm has an additional advantage having no contamination at its inner depth under inhibitory condition. There are a limited number of methods available for determining the kinetic coefficients required for solution of the model of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor.

In the process design of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor, the kinetic coefficients act as an essential tool for predicting the substrate utilization and biomass growth under a spe-

cific condition. The biomass yield coefficient (Y) indicates the portion of the biomass growth from the utilization of substrates. Specific biomass growth rate (μ) represents the biomass growth rate per unit biomass per day. Maximum value of specific biomass growth rate (μ_{max}) is attained when substrates are not in limiting condition. Half velocity constant (K) is the substrate concentration corresponding to half of maximum specific biomass growth rate (μ_{max}). The maximum specific substrate utilization rate (k) represents the substrate utilization rate per day per unit biomass in respect of μ_{max} . Biomass decay coefficient (b_d) is the rate of biomass loss due to endogenous decay and is taken into consideration for determining the net biomass growth rate. In the biofilm process, the rate of total biomass loss (b_t) consists of the rates of biomass shear loss (b_s) and biomass decay (b_d). Y , k , K , b_t , b_s and b_d are the kinetic coefficients required for the solution of a specific biofilm model.

Substrate mass balance is accomplished with the simultaneous occurrence of both diffusion and utilization of substrates. The molecular diffusion coefficient of the substrate

in water (D) and in the biofilm (D_f) represents internal mass transport resistance in the bulk liquid and in the biofilm respectively. The thickness of the effective diffusion layer of the bulk liquid (L) represents the external mass transport resistance. The biomass concentration (X_f) in the biofilm can be determined from the total biofilm thickness (L_f). Biofilm thickness primarily depends on the substrate concentration in the bulk liquid and the liquid hydraulics. The biomass per unit surface area i.e. ($X_f L_f$) is constant indicating the steady state condition of biofilm.

Various research studies have been reported on modeling of biofilm reactor²⁻¹⁹ but no specific method was developed for determining the kinetic coefficients. Indeed, the kinetic coefficients are needful for solving the biofilm model and hence for the process design of the biofilm reactor.

A kinetic study was performed in an aerobic biofilm bioreactor for evaluation of efficiency of COD removal from organic wastewater²⁰. The half velocity constant (K) was determined from the experimental results using Monod's kin-

etics. The inhibition kinetics was used in another research work for predicting the response of biofilms to toxic compounds in wastewater²¹. Although the relationship between the effectiveness factor of biofilm and the half velocity constant (K) was shown, no guideline was stipulated for arriving the values of K . Hsien *et al.*¹⁵ has conducted one batch test for determining the kinetic coefficients for simulation study in a biofilm reactor. Therefore, development of kinetics for an aerobic biofilm reactor for the treatment of wastewater is extremely important. The present method employs a series of biofilm model equations complying Monod's growth kinetics. The graphical procedures for evaluating the kinetics coefficients like K , k , Y , b_t , b_s and b_d for substrate removal and biomass growth have been presented sequentially.

Materials and methods

The schematic diagram of biofilm model considering purely attached biomass is shown in Fig. 1. The concept of biofilm model is based upon three basic assumptions, i.e. (i) the nature of the kinetics for substrate utilization in suspended

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of biofilm model.

growth and attached growth are of similar nature, (ii) external substrate transport from the bulk liquid to the biofilm through biofilm liquid interface follows Fick's 1st law of molecular diffusion, (iii) the substrate transport within the biofilm follows the Fick's 2nd law of molecular diffusion. Now, the external mass transport according to Fick's first law,

$$J = \frac{D}{L} \times (S_0 - S_s) \quad (1)$$

where, J = substrate flux into the biofilm ($\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2/\text{day}$), D = molecular diffusion coefficient in liquid (cm^2/day), L = thickness of effective diffusion layer (cm), S_0 , S_s = substrate concentrations in the bulk liquid and at the biofilm liquid interface respectively (mg/cm^3).

Now, from the substrate mass balance within the biofilm is

$$S_0 - S_w - aJ\theta = 0 \quad (2)$$

where, a = specific surface area of supporting media (cm^{-1}), θ = hydraulic detention time (h), S_w = effluent substrate concentration (mg/cm^3).

Therefore, from eq. (2) it can be written that,

$$J = \frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta}$$

Again the mass balance equation for substrate in the biofilm considering Monod's' kinetics represents

$$\frac{d^2 S_f}{dz^2} = \frac{kX_f S_f}{D_f (K + S_f)}$$

where, S_f = substrate concentration at a point in the biofilm (mg/cm^3), k = maximum specific rate of substrate use (per day), X_f = active biomass density within the biofilm (mg/cm^3), D_f = molecular diffusion coefficient of the substrate in the biofilm (cm^2/day), K = half velocity coefficient (mg/cm^3).

Referring Fig. 1, the boundary conditions for solving above 2nd order differential equation may be taken as,

(i) At the attachment surface (i.e. at $z=0$) there will be no flux, i.e. $\frac{dS_f}{dz} = 0$.

(ii) At the biofilm/water interface i.e. at $z=L_e$,

$$J = D_f \times \frac{dS_f}{dz} = D \times \frac{(S_0 - S_s)}{L}$$

Now the solution of above 2nd order differential equation on substrate utilization within the biofilm considering both the boundary conditions yields

$$J = \sqrt{2kX_f D_f (S_s - S_w) + K \cdot \ln \frac{(K + S_w)}{(K + S_s)}} \quad (3)$$

or $J^2 = 2kX_f D_f (S_s - S_w) + K \cdot \ln \frac{(K + S_w)}{(K + S_s)}$

Analytical procedure for determining the kinetic coefficients:

In order to determine the kinetic coefficients, the biomass growth curve, eqs. (1), (2) and (3) can be systematically used in following Steps.

Step 1:

$$\mu = \frac{X_2 - X_1}{X_1 \theta} \quad (4)$$

μ = specific growth rate of biomass for biofilm bioreactor (h^{-1}), X_2 = final biomass density for attached phase at the end of batch period (mg/cc), X_1 = initial biomass density for attached phase at the end of batch period (mg/cc), θ = batch period under consideration (h). Biomass density can be determined by washing the biofilm attached surface with 25 ml 0.1 (N) NaOH after heating the solution at 80°C (Cox *et al.*, 1999, Lazarova *et al.*, 1994) and subsequently by measuring the protein content with Lowry's method.

Step 2:

The ' μ ' values can be plotted in Y-axis with respect to ' S_w ' values in X-axis, which should have an ascending asymptotic nature as shown in Fig. 2. The half-velocity constant K can be obtained corresponding to half of the maximum specific growth rate, i.e. μ_{max} or μ_m , as indicated in the same figure.

Fig. 2. Biomass growth curve for determination of half velocity constant K.

Fig. 3. Biofilm growth for determination of k and Y.

Step 3:

Using eqs. (1), (2) and (3),

$$\left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta}\right)^2 = 2kX_f D_f \left[\left\{ S_0 - \frac{L}{D} \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta} \right) - S_w \right\} + K \cdot \ln \left\{ \frac{k + S_w}{k + S_0 - \frac{L}{D} \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta} \right)} \right\} \right]$$

Now, $\left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta}\right)^2$ values can be plotted with respect to

$$2kX_f D_f \left[\left\{ S_0 - \frac{L}{D} \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta} \right) - S_w \right\} + \right.$$

$$\left. K \cdot \ln \left\{ \frac{k + S_w}{k + S_0 - \frac{L}{D} \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{a\theta} \right)} \right\} \right]$$
 and a best-fit line can be

drawn as shown in Fig. 3. A best-fit line passing through the origin will result in the value of k.

Step 4:

Now the total biofilm thickness can be estimated as $L_f =$

$$\frac{JY}{X_f b_t}, \text{ where, } L_f = \text{total biofilm thickness, } J = \text{substrate}$$

flux, $X_f =$ biofilm density, $b_t =$ overall specific biofilm loss rate in (h^{-1}) , $\mu_m = kY$ or $Y = \mu_m/k$. Therefore, the value of L_f can

be plotted with respect to $\frac{JY}{X_f}$ or $\left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{X_f a\theta}\right) Y$ as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Biomass balance for attached growth for determination of b_t .

Step 5:

In order to determine the shear loss coefficient (b_s), the sloughed off biomass from the attached surface may be equated to the final suspended biomass after each batch

period in the reactor, i.e. $Y \cdot a \cdot \theta \cdot J \cdot \frac{b_s}{b_t} = X$ or $\frac{Y a \theta J}{b_t} = \frac{X}{b_s}$, or,

$$\frac{Y(S_0 - S_w)}{b_t} = \frac{X}{b_s}, \text{ where } \theta = \text{batch period, } X = \text{final sus-}$$

pended biomass in the reactor. Now, $Y \cdot \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{b_t}\right)$ can be plotted with respect to X as shown in Fig. 5. The slope of the best-fit line will denote the value of $(1/b_s)$.

Fig. 5. Determination of b_s (Biomass shear loss).

Results and discussion

Illustrative example:

In the laboratory, semi-batch study on municipal wastewater in an aerobic biofilm bioreactor in three consecutive days was performed at an interval of 3 h. ' μ ' is calculated

$$\mu = \frac{(X_{\text{attached}2} - X_{\text{attached}1})}{(X_{\text{attached}1})\theta}$$

from the expression as shown in Table 1. Consequently, ' μ ' vs. ' S_w ' graph is plotted as shown in Fig. 6 to find out μ_m or μ_{max} and K .

From Fig. 6, μ_{max} and K are obtained as $\mu_{\text{max}} = 0.11 \text{ h}^{-1} = 2.64 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $K = 60 \text{ mg/L} = 0.06 \text{ mg/cc}$. Now, the values of $(S_0 - S_w/a)^2$ are plotted against $2 \times X_f \times D_f \times \theta^2 \times [S_0 - L/D \{ (S_0 - S_w)/a \theta \} - S_w + K \cdot \ln \{ (K + S_w) / (K + S_0 - L/D \{ (S_0 - S_w)/a \theta \}) \}]$ as shown in Fig. 7 to determine the value of k and Y .

From the Fig. 7, it is observed that $k = 2.6 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Therefore, $Y = \mu_{\text{max}}/k = 2.64/2.6 = 0.99$. Now, $L_f \theta X_f$ are plotted

Fig. 6. Biomass growth curve for determination of half velocity constant K .

Fig. 7. Biofilm growth for determination of k and Y .

against $(S_0 - S_w)Y/a$ as shown in Fig. 8 to determine the value of b_t .

Fig. 8. Biomass balance for attached growth for determination of b_t .

Table 1. Batch study results of biofilm reactor

Batch slot	Batch period (θ , h)	Biomass in attached film (X_{attached} , mg)	COD (S_w , mg/L)
1st day	0	278	112
	3	370	92
	6	453	82
	9	532	79
2nd day	0	470	100
	3	657	78
	6	691	70
	9	768	60
3rd day	0	408	130
	3	672	100
	6	840	80
	9	888	75

It is observed from Fig. 8 that $1/b_t = 0.501$ day, hence total biomass loss rate, $b_t = 1.996 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Now, $Y(S_0 - S_w)/b_t$ are plotted against X as shown in Fig. 9 to determine the value of b_s .

Fig. 9. Determination of b_s (biomass shear loss).

From Fig. 9, $1/b_s = 0.552$ day, hence biomass shear loss, $b_s = 1.81 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Hence biomass decay $b_d = 0.186 \text{ day}^{-1}$.

Discussion

The specific growth curve of biomass as shown in Fig. 2 essentially depicts the Monod's kinetics, which is valid for non-inhibitory environment. In case of inhibitory environment, the specific growth curve will show a maximum value (i.e. μ_m) and then it will move downward. As the specific growth curve significantly influences the values of μ_m and K , it should be plotted with a set of data as large as possible. The maximum specific substrate utilization rate (k) can be calculated from the slope of Fig. 3, provided the biomass density of the biofilm reactor is known. On the other hand, the ' b_t ' value evaluated from the slope of Fig. 4 represents the rate of total biomass loss in the biofilm reactor. The rate of shear loss

(b_s) is evaluated by plotting $Y \cdot \left(\frac{S_0 - S_w}{b_t} \right)$ against X as

shown in Fig. 5. In these cases also the slope of the 'best-fit line' considerably influence the values of b_s and b_d and therefore and Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 should be drawn with a large set of data. The use of the present method in determining the kinetic coefficients for the treatment of municipal wastewater in a biofilm reactor clearly demonstrates its efficacy and com-

patibility. All such kinetic data also indicated good removal performance of organic substrate in the biofilm reactor.

Conclusion

So far, no simple method for determining the kinetic coefficients of the biofilm bioreactor was developed in any earlier research. An attempt was made to present a simple method with straight line equations and graphical representation for determining the kinetic coefficients of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor. The proposed development for kinetic coefficients of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor finds its relevance for its process design. The proposed method is an accurate, fast and simplistic one to find out the kinetic coefficients of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor. It is possible to simply calculate the kinetic coefficients from the graphs either from the intercepts of both X and Y-axis or from the slope of the graph applying mass balance equations both for substrates and biomass. All necessary kinetic coefficients like K , k , Y , b_s , b_t and b_d can be determined by the method proposed for the modelling of an aerobic biofilm bioreactor (Sarkar and Mazumder, 2014). In reality the application of biofilm bioreactor model suffers due to lack of accuracy of kinetic models and uncertainty in the kinetic parameters. Successful modelling of the biofilm bioreactor therefore requires accurate determination of bio-kinetic parameters.

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